

ANALYSIS OF RECURRENT DEFECTS IN THE EXECUTION OF CERAMIC COATINGS CLADDING IN BUILDING CONSTRUCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a series of results that emerged from the implementation of the first phase of a continuous improvement study applied to a particular housing construction project. As a result of the study, it was possible to determine the relationship between the most common construction defects regarding ceramic cladding. Out of the seven statistical analysis tools, the four most relevant ones have been selected and systematically used during the present work: data collection sheet, stratification, histogram, and Pareto Diagram. The results show that there exist 25 main types that group the diverse detected -and most recurring- incidences in housing construction. From the total sum of accounted defects, 87.5% are caused during the execution process, while almost half of the occurrences -47.6%- is caused or derived by improper grout preparation or faulty application. This relation of defects can be used by the professionals of the construction industry in order to implement continuous improvement projects focused on minimizing failures. It can also be used as check list to carry out the quality control of ceramic cladding.

Key words: *continuous improvement, quality management, construction failures, construction defects, floors, tiles.*

INTRODUCTION

The increasingly competitive construction market requires AEC firms to satisfy the needs and expectations of their clients to deliver high-quality, error-free products (Flynn, et al., 1995) (Anderson, et al., 2014). In order to fulfill these requirements, construction-related companies certify their management process according to the ISO 9001 Regulation, which considers total quality upon product delivery to the final client a core issue in the Continuous Improvement process.

The Continuous Improvement is carried out through case studies and real projects. According to AENOR (Spanish Association for Standardization and Certification) a Continuous Improvement project is a *“Project selected by competent organisms from within the organization, which aim to eliminate or reduce the difference between the best-case scenario and a real situation related to one or more improvement opportunities”* (AENOR, 2004). Therefore the main focus of Continuous Improvement is on identifying possible error-prone issues and determining the precise corrective measures that would allow to prevent future failures or relevant mistakes.

Works on Total Quality began to be published back in the eighties in the context of the Industrial Sector. The relevance of Continuous Improvement was already heavily emphasized as a process that would imply the cooperation of all members within an organization, stating the importance of knowledge and adequate training at all levels of production (Ishikawa, 1985), (Reed, et al., 2000).

Nevertheless, the complex nature of the Construction sector -where the unique, non-serialized products, and the “nomadic”, ever-changing working environment are key distinctive issues- makes a direct translation of the above mentioned work hardly possible. In other words, it does not make sense to intend to directly apply the lessons learned from other industries onto the construction sector as the stated differences

between the sectors stand out for themselves when it comes to implement Quality aspects (Josephson & Hammarlund, 1999), (García, 2001). Yet it is precisely this complexity in the building process what makes it necessary to define and deploy several processes of Total Quality and Continuous Improvement that ultimately allow for a more compelling service to clients and user satisfaction.

Beside the difficulties that are inherent to the construction sector, it is worth pointing out internal firm management. Without a clear support of the organization and the reasonable training of employees, it is not possible to implement Continuous Improvement Projects (Anand, et al., 2009). In this case, it is the senior management department who is responsible for steadily looking after the enhancement of the management and production processes of their firms (AENOR, 2004), (Membrado, 2002). Furthermore, it is necessary that firms are not tied to immediate result-analysis and must take into account that continuous improvement is a long-haul process (Bessant, et al., 2001).

Nevertheless, it has been widely proven that the implementation of Total Quality aspects in the Construction Sector allows to not only diminish the percentages of defects in selected end product items –therefore minimizing reparation costs in a significant manner-, but also to build up the international reputation of the firm (Lester, et al., 1992), (Merli, 1993), (Lopez, 2006).

Several authors have studied defects in construction related to this particular concern, and delivering important and reliable information on the most recurrent defects that helps plan preventive actions (Gardez et al., 2012), (Gardez et al., 2012), (Neto & Brito, 2012), (Pereida, et al., 2011), (Silvestre & Brito, 2009), (Silvestre & Brito, 2011), (Silva, et al., 2011), (Rodrigues, et al., 2011), (Macarulla, et al., 2013). Chew's work, for instance, analyzes failure in the adherence of outer ceramic cladding of building facades

and the defects of every single craft involved the execution of wet areas in buildings (Chew, 1999), (Chew, 2005).

Despite all the previous studies, there is no work that ultimately analyses in depth all defects associated to ceramic cladding (including also slabs and floors) inside a dwelling. Therefore, the main aim of this investigation is to determine which are the most relevant and/or frequent construction defects in ceramic cladding in housing projects at the stage of pre-delivery to the final building users. In order to do that, a first phase of a Continuous Development project has been thoroughly carried out over the construction of a series of housing units in Madrid, Spain. The work hereby exposed intends to become a relevant example of internal failure detection through the mechanisms of control of a construction company.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There exist numerous quality tools for Continuous Improvement evaluation and implementation: FMEA (Failure Mode Effects Analysis), QFD (Quality Function Deployment), Six Sigma, or the seven basic quality tools defined by Ishikawa (Ishikawa, 1985), which are widely recognized by other relevant authors. These tools are: (1) Pareto diagram, (2) cause-effect diagrams, (3) stratification, (4) check list (or data collection sheet), (5) histograms, (6) dispersion diagrams and (7) control graphs.

Other authors share the same view. In an international study carried out by Terziovsky and Sohal that includes a survey to 1200 managers responsible for manufacturing organizations they conclude that firms tend to use these basic quality control tools instead of other, more complex options –such as FMEA or QFD. This study includes a series of countries, accounting for Australia, Denmark, Finland, Sweden, The Netherlands, and United Kingdom (Terziovski & Sohal, 2000).

In our specific case study –Continuous Improvement Projects applied to housing construction-, it suffices to use the following four out of the afore mentioned seven basic quality tools (Del Solar & Del Río, 2014): check list, stratification, histograms, and Pareto diagrams –which best deal with the activities that must be carried out during this phase-, beside spreadsheets –in order to obtain the percentages that help identify the relative importance and recurrence of each defect.

There is therefore no need to use cause-effect diagrams, since the defect causes are easily derived through observation by a trained eye. Furthermore, control graphs are used in industrial fabrication processes, and dispersion diagrams are intended for variable behavior prediction in statistical analysis.

The methodology presented in this article is divided according to the following steps:

1. Building site selection: a total of 625 units from 10 different housing projects were inspected. The units were selected to present similar features, paying special attention to certain features that include, but are not limited to size, quality, and construction type. Also, all units were built within a limited timeframe, from 2009 to 2012, which ensures a constrained regulation system and minimized differences in building materials and methodologies.

2. Data collection sheets:

6963 incidences were accounted for that belonged to the ceramic cladding craft. The quality controls were performed once the work units were finished and right before the final delivery to the owners, as shown in Table 1.

3. Stratification: The stratification is put into effect in order to be able to analyze the obtained incidences. It is a method that consists of “the subdivision of the collected data into homogeneous groups that allow for a better comprehension of the phenomena being analyzed” (Galgano, 1995). In this sense, the obtained

recurrences can be classified in two main levels: three main groups (numbered “i”, “ii”, and “iii”), and twelve subgroups (named after the alphabet from “a” to “l”):

- i. Execution process: Failures or defects due to incorrect or improper praxis during execution
 - a. Piece allocation or stake problems: failure derived from errors or poor execution during the placement of the cladding.
 - b. Selection or material supply: flaws that emerge due to poor praxis upon material reception on site or material selection prior to its use.
 - c. Placement of tiles: mistakes in the tile placement process.
 - d. Faulty grout processing or incorrect/insufficient hardening time during the execution.
 - e. Flaws in the refill of shafts and voids for building systems.
 - f. Site cleaning: mistakes that could have been avoided or resolved when cleaning the site.
- ii. Craft collision or lack of sequential planning: errors produced as a consequence of works on other crafts.
 - g. Breakage or flakes when placing elements on ceramic pieces or tiles.
 - h. Lack of preparation for mechanical or electrical system fixtures: fixture holes have not been prepared in walls, can be easily moved, or are not properly aligned with the cladding, thus preventing a correct finish.

- i. Setting out of mechanical and electrical fixtures on site: the fixtures are not located where they were planned, forcing the need to modify the originally planned cladding distribution to accommodate their position.
- j. Wall misalignments: cladding support is misaligned and pops out when covered by the cladding pieces or tiles.
- iii. Unpredictable errors: flaws that cannot be prevented due to their accidental nature or unintended cause.
- k. Missing pieces or elements. Missing pieces in hardly accessible or not visible parts of the building due to carelessness, inattention, or other direct worker-related mistakes.
- l. Breaks, tears, or flakes in materials caused by hits or unknown causes.

Furthermore, the above presented subgroups can be divided into 25 defects (which are enumerated below), as shown in Table 2.

- 4. Data analysis: it is crucial to perform a two-fold analysis, taking not only into account the volume of incidences or recurrences, but also the reparation cost associated to certain works, since a small volume of defects can occasionally derive in great repair costs (Galgano, 1995). For this reason, the hereby presented work calculates the relative incidence of each instance –percentages, as well as the cost evaluation for all three studied levels. To facilitate the calculation of the repair costs, the study uses the unitary prices provided by the construction firm.

Having information on repair costs can also facilitate the establishment of price adjustment linked to the actual quality of the products, as a mechanism that may contribute to stimulate construction companies by setting incentives or penalizations

linked to the final quality of the product upon delivery. (Burati, et al., 2003), (Praticò, et al., 2012).

Additionally, the incidences with highest impact or relevance will be evaluated and established according to the theories of the Pareto Diagram, which gives meaningful information to “*determine the frequency or relative impact of different problems or causes*” and helps “*focus on vital questions by sorting them by importance terms*” (Chang & Niezwiecki, 1999). In other words, those defects accounting for more than 80% at either end –instance volume or repair cost- will be identified as the main targets to consider and given the highest priority in order to achieve a significant reduction in the defects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 3, most ceramic cladding defects are due to faulty execution, accounting a total of 9.74 incidences by housing unit (i/du) out of a total of 11.14 i/du, which constitutes the 87.5% of the total volume of occurrences and 90.1% of the repair costs. Applying the Pareto Diagram, this means that it is possible to achieve a quite significant reduction of the defect instances by stablishing execution and control criteria adapted to the most repetitive faults. These result in error-reducing strategies that might be easily integrated within construction firms’ quality management operating standards of workflows.

These are very relevant results, as it could otherwise not be possible to apply corrective and prevention measures with sufficient guarantee of being successful in the reduction of defects. The variety of situations that would be required in order to combine all possible scenarios would simply be too vast and extensive. Furthermore, the diversity of

crafts involved in the different construction sites and projects would make it impossible to standardize and plan preventive actions that would incorporate all case studies.

Table 4 shows a summary of the incidences classified according to the 12 subgroups defined previously.

Results throw that 80% of the total volume of incidences belong to the following 4 subgroups: faulty grout (d), mep equipment shafts/void refills (d), piece allocation (a), and breaks or flakes (l). Three out of the four refer to defective execution processes (main group “i”), where special attention must be paid. The other one is rather difficult to solve, as it belongs to the “unpredictable errors” group (main group “iii”), which turns into less capacity to solve related problems.

Regarding costs, 80% gathers the following three subgroups, all classified under the “Execution process” group: allocation of pieces (a), faulty grouts (b), and placement of pieces (c).

More specifically, the “piece allocation” and “grout faults”, are two of the most recurrent defect groups, and also cause high economic repair costs. Given this combination of facts, construction firms should focus their efforts on preventive strategies that aim at resolving these precise issues. This would allow them to easily obtain better results as the impact on defects would be outstanding.

Regarding the stratification of result data in the 25 defect types, table 5 shows clearly that defect types [17], [18], [25] and [3] concentrate also 80% of the total volume of incidences. More precisely, defects in type [17] account for 29.1% of the total amount of incidences, which is a similar percentage to that obtained by Chew in his study (Chew, 2005), which states that 21% of defect found in wet areas of houses are due to faults in grout preparation, being the most recurrent defect from among the 14 that his study analyses.

Concerning the defect types that gather 80% of repair costs, they are as follows (sorted from higher to lower impact):

- Replacement of selected cladding tiles due to incorrect cutting. [3]
- Replacement of grout caused by faulty execution. [17]
- Replacement of single pieces that may have been accidentally hit, punched, scratched. [25]
- Replacement of cladding in any of the sides of the bath tub or shower tray. [2]
- Replacement of several tiles due to relevant uneven surfacing. [14]
- Replacement of several ceramic tiles due to bad application or faulty fixation. Hollow zones. [11]

In short, the study yields that defects derived from piece placement or faulty grout preparation (types [3] and [17]) sum up 58.9% of total repair costs. These types have also a relatively large presence in the volume of incidences. In addition to that, they belong to the group “Execution process”.

Generally, most recurrent defects, both regarding repair cost and volume, are included in the “Execution process” group, which makes it possible to establish working methodologies and specific control procedures to avoid further presence in the future.

In this sense, many of the ISO 9001 certified construction firms that already implement such control procedures are unsuccessful, since working teams are immersed in internal paralyzing administrative plans (Badía & Bellido, 1999).

As a consequence of the above, the results obtained in the present study would only solve part of the problem, as it would be a core requirement to implement workflow and control procedures (check lists) directed at minimizing the defects due to piece fixations and faulty grout execution. Approximately 56.7% of the instances, and 58.9% of the repair cost would be thereby suppressed.

CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the study, we can state that:

- The incidences detected in ceramic cladding can be grouped in 25 defect types, although it would be sufficient to focus the attention in the following 6 (which combine 80% of the incidences), so as to achieve a meaningful reduction in the flaws emerging from the studied activities:
 - Replacement of cladding tiles in bathtub or shower trays at their corners or edges. Errors in the piece layout on site, shallow rows of tiles right above the tub with high risk of leakage or accidental detachment of pieces due to insufficient grout fixation area. Poorly finished area.
 - Replacement of specific ceramic tiles due to faulty cut of pieces, excessive visibility of joints meeting windows, doors, gutters, electric fixtures; spot lights or lighting fixtures; water intake piping including wash basin, sinks, bidet, and toilet tanks; water drainage pipes of kitchen and bathroom sinks; hot water in heating appliances; floor drains; vent gratings; draining pipes in terraces and other wet areas. Poor finishing or insufficient coverage by corner trims.
 - Replacement of several tiles derived from faulty fixation. Hollow zones.
 - Replacement of specific tiles due to uneven surfacing (differences higher than 2 mm).
 - Grout replacement due to poor execution: open zones or areas with holes, scratched, or excessive amount of grout in any of the following joint types: flooring-wall; Wall-ceiling; cladding-trim pieces; cladding-bathtubs; around fixtures (sockets, switches, telephone, TV...)

- Replacement of single pieces that may have been punched, hit, scratched, marked, or stained during the execution of diverse construction processes by other crafts.
- 87.5% of total volume of incidences in ceramic cladding and 90.1% of the total repair cost thereby derived proceed from mistakes during the execution process. This fact makes it possible to take preventive actions and set up control procedures at execution time to prevent them from occurring.
- 47.6% of the volume of incidences are due to faulty grout preparation, which account themselves for a notable 29.1% of the total repair cost for all incidences combined.
- 29.8% of the total repair cost of all incidences related to ceramic cladding is due to the need of replacing single pieces that may have been improperly cut or changed during execution due to shifts in layout planning on site.

It can therefore be stated that it is possible to enhance current construction trends by implementing meaningful preventive measures and actions based on good construction practices focusing on avoiding the repetition of these defects through workflow procedures and control methodologies to be implemented on specific work units at every stage of the execution process. Furthermore, as these are preventive actions, further internal documentation that may be required by a firm's operating standards or other certifications may be avoided, deriving in a more efficient overall workflow.

Using the hereby proposed list of type defects, professionals can define preventive actions to help reduce the number of incidences. It is recommended to also use this listing as a sort of check list to facilitate the inspection works of ceramic cladding.

Furthermore, it is important to point out that the present study focuses on housing construction projects. This type of construction has many common features, such as the

limited type of spaces the houses are subdivided into, the use of similar work packages and material across different projects. This particularities make the study specially relevant to this specific typology of construction.

The methodology proposed by the study can be reproduced in other trades involved in housing or other construction projects –retail buildings, offices, hospitals...- in such a way that it could be possible to establish listings of defects for all cases.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank ARPADA Company, particularly the Department of Environment and Quality and the Department of Projects, for providing the data needed for this study.

NOTATION LIST

The following symbols and abbreviations are used in this paper:

- AEC = Architecture Engineering Construction.
- AENOR = Spanish Association for Standardization and Certification.
- FMEA = Failure Mode Effects Analysis.
- i = units.
- i/du = incidences by housing.
- ISO = International Organization for Standardization.
- mm = milimitres.
- QFD = Quality Function Deployment.
- \$ = dollar
- $\$/du$ = dollar by housing.

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TABLES

Table 1. Schedule of Inspections

Project/site	2009				2010					2011					2012										
	s	o	n	d	j	f	m	a	m	j	j	a	s	o	n	d	j	f	m	a	m	j	j	a	
01 Alcobendas	X																								
02 Móstoles	X																								
03 Vicálvaro					X	X																			
04 Navalcarnero							X																		
05 Alcorcón								X	X																
06 Móstoles 2												X													
07 Alcorcón 2												X	X												
08 Alcobendas 2																						X	X		
09 Vallecas																						X	X		
10 Boadilla																									X

Table 2: Defect types detected in ceramic cladding		
Incidence Group/ Subgroup	Defect types	
i: Execution Process	a	[1] Replacement of ceramic tiles in areas close to perimeter or edges. The flooring is not properly attached or finished (it either falls too short and does not reach the cladding, or does not go underneath the cladding tiles), joints are too prominent or irregular. The last tile row is too shallow and does not continue beyond the suspended ceiling; this solution is likely to fail in areas where doors are present, as their insufficient area does not allow for a correct fixation.
		[2] Replacement of cladding in any of the sides of the bath tub or shower tray on site placement mistake, tile stripe too narrow with possible detachment of pieces as a consequence of improper adherence surface areas. Improperly finished areas.
		[3] Replacement of selected cladding tiles due to incorrect cutting, excessive width of joints meeting windows, doors, gutters, electrical mechanisms or fixtures; lighting points; water fixtures in both bathroom and kitchen sinks and tubs, toilet tanks, bidets, flushes, drain pipes, water faucets; input of hot water for radiators and heating systems; drain traps; ventilation gratings; water drainage pipes in terraces and other exterior areas –prepared for dumping clothes or other uses. Unacceptable finishing conditions and/or cladding insufficiently covered by corner trims.
		[4] Punctual replacement of single ceramic pieces due to excessive overhang, risk of break, poor flooring finishing in edges meeting facade walls or other enclosure elements (lattice, trellis...)
		[5] Punctual replacement of flooring due to “last-minute” or unpredicted pavement material change (motivating significant thickness variation-related issues), undesired tile patches seen on the wrong side of closed doors.
		[6] Replacement of several ceramic tiles due to improper on-site layout planning or execution, unaligned or excessive joint visibility/width.
		[7] Replacement of bathtub/shower tray corner brackets when exposed tile sides, undesired finishing look and/or danger of cutting edges.
		[8] Replacement of baseboards in door frame joints, or wall kinks of various types, which show tile sides that are prone to cuts (visible cuts in stoneware tiles).
	b	[9] Replacement of flooring due to unexpected hue changes, defects in tile patterns or faulty manufacturing.
		[10] Grout replacement due to color grading mistakes, different to projected or selected color(s).
		[11] Replacement of several ceramic tiles due to bad application or faulty fixation. Hollow zones.
		[12] Reparation or rework of grout in order to hide joint marks by using wedges or paper instead of standard cross-shaped tile separators which stay visible after cladding placement.
		[13] Replacement of specific tiles due to uneven surfacing or presence of lines (wide visible direct lines on tile surface, mostly result of production line bars)
	c	[14] Replacement of several tiles due to uneven surfacing or presence of lines
		[15] Replacement of several tiles due to defects in the planarity of the cladding surface. Visible bumps, bulges or similar defects.
		[16] Replacement of flooring due to puddles, presence of water on the surface, or incorrect pipe slopes that cause water stagnation.
	d	[17] Replacement of grout caused by faulty execution: void or open areas, pinched surfaces, visible cracks, or excessive amount of grout in joints between walls and floors, walls and ceilings, cladding and corner reinforcements, cladding and shower trays, electrical fixtures (sockets, power switches, telephone sockets, TV...)
	e	[18] Refill of possible openings or clearances between sanitary water intake pipes and cladding (sinks, toilet, bidet, washing machines, dishwasher, basins...)
	f	[19] Cleaning of marks, lines, scratches or similar deficiencies due to unavoidable contact between pieces or changes of layout distributions on-site.
ii: Interference of other crafts	g	[20] Replacement of certain ceramic tiles caused by breaks or superficial flakes caused while anchoring or attaching shower parts (flanges, arms, rings or such) or doors to walls.
	h	[21] Use of grout to fill holes, voids, or clearances between water pipes/plugs (sinks, toilet, bidet, washing machines, dishwasher, basins...) and the finished cladding, or correctly adjusting wall trims, escutcheons, and similar finishing pieces.
	i	[22] Selected replacement of a few pieces of cladding by layout errors, eccentric or misaligned lighting fixtures, or light spots that fall inside secure/protection volume definitions.
	j	[23] Replacement of ceramic tiles due to misaligned interior walls or partitions, especially those from shafts and others alike.
iii: Unpredictable errors	k	[24] Placement of ceramic tiles where they have not been placed (behind doors or curtains).
	l	[25] Replacement of single pieces that may have been accidentally hit, punched, scratched, or flaked by interferences with other crafts on site.

Table 3: Number, proportions, and cost of incidences classified according to the 3 main groups						
625 HOUSING UNITS						
Incidence group	i [units]	i/du	% relative	Total cost (\$)	\$/du	% relative
i. Execution process	6.090	9,74	87,5%	194.065,26	310,50	90,1%
ii. Interference of other crafts	165	0,26	2,4%	4.886,18	7,82	2,3%
iii. Unpredictable errors	708	1,13	10,2%	16.323,50	26,12	7,6%
Grand Total	6.963	11,14		215.274,94	344,44	

Table 4: Number and cost of incidences classified by operational subgroups							
625 HOUSING UNITS							
Incidence subgroup	i [units]	i/du	% relative	Total Cost (\$)	\$/du	% relative	
i: Execution process	a. Piece allocation.	863	1,38	12,4%	86.523,38	138,44	40,2%
	b. Material Selection.	342	0,55	4,9%	9.635,49	15,41	4,5%
	c. Placement of pieces/fixations.	338	0,54	4,9%	28.742,95	45,99	13,4%
	d. Grout faults.	3.311	5,30	47,6%	62.677,67	100,28	29,1%
	e. Refill of voids around shafts or equipment pipes.	960	1,54	13,8%	5.360,20	8,57	2,5%
	f. Site cleaning.	276	0,44	4,0%	1.125,56	1,80	0,5%
ii: Interference of other crafts	g. Break or flakes at time of placement	30	0,05	0,4%	674,74	1,08	0,3%
	h. Lack of preparation in mechanical or electrical equipment.	70	0,11	1,0%	390,85	0,63	0,2%
	i. Setting out of mechanical and electrical fixtures.	43	0,07	0,6%	967,13	1,55	0,4%
	j. Interior Wall misalignment.	22	0,04	0,3%	2.853,45	4,56	1,3%
iii: Unpredictable errors	k. Missing pieces.	17	0,03	0,2%	781,90	1,25	0,4%
	l. Breaks and flake (others)	691	1,11	9,9%	15.541,61	24,86	7,2%
Total	6.963	11,14		215.274,94	344,44		

Table 5: Number and cost of each incidence sorted by type.

625 HOSUING UNITS									
Defect Types		i [units]	i/du	% relative	Unitary cost (\$)	Total Cost (\$)	\$/du	% relative	
i: Execution process	a	[1] Un. Replacement ...perimeter zones...	35	0,06	0,5%	42,58 \$	1.490,26	2,38	0,7%
		[2] Un. Replacement ... bathtub edges...	102	0,16	1,5%	120,52 \$	12.293,42	19,67	5,7%
		[3] Un. Replacement...due to cut/placement errors...	637	1,02	9,1%	100,82 \$	64.221,32	102,75	29,8%
		[4] Un. Replacement ... excessive overhang...	4	0,01	0,1%	52,66 \$	210,62	0,34	0,1%
		[5] Un. Replacement ... pavement material...	9	0,01	0,1%	46,48 \$	418,29	0,67	0,2%
		[6] Un. Replacement... too wide joints...	29	0,05	0,4%	220,08 \$	6.382,43	10,21	3,0%
		[7] Un. Replacement of corner bracket in bathtub...	28	0,04	0,4%	43,05 \$	1.205,42	1,93	0,6%
		[8] Un. Replacement of baseboards...at door frame...	19	0,03	0,3%	15,87 \$	301,61	0,48	0,1%
	b	[9] Un. Replacement... floor due to color grading...	40	0,06	0,6%	97,96 \$	3.918,59	6,27	1,8%
		[10] Un. Replacement of grout due to color errors...	302	0,48	4,3%	18,93 \$	5.716,90	9,14	2,7%
		[11] Un. Replacement due to improper placement...	29	0,05	0,4%	220,08 \$	6.382,43	10,21	3,0%
		[12] Un. Repair of grout due to excessive joint...	39	0,06	0,6%	18,93 \$	738,28	1,18	0,3%
	c	[13] Un. Replacement...due to uneven surface	192	0,31	2,8%	22,49 \$	4.318,36	6,91	2,0%
		[14] Un. Replacement... several surfacing problems	55	0,09	0,8%	220,08 \$	12.104,61	19,37	5,6%
		[15] Un. Replacement... planarity defects...	18	0,03	0,3%	220,08 \$	3.961,51	6,34	1,8%
		[16] Un. Replacement due to puddles...	5	0,01	0,1%	247,55 \$	1.237,76	1,98	0,6%
	d	[17] Un. Replacement of grout due to faulty execution	3.311	5,30	47,6%	18,93 \$	62.677,67	100,28	29,1%
	e	[18] Un. Refill of sanitary water intake piping...	960	1,54	13,8%	5,58 \$	5.360,20	8,57	2,5%
	f	[19] Un. Cleaning of scratches, lines ...	276	0,44	4,0%	4,08 \$	1.125,56	1,80	0,5%
ii: Interference of other crafts	g	[20] Un. Replacement ... break... shower support...	30	0,05	0,4%	22,49 \$	674,74	1,08	0,3%
	h	[21] Un. Use of grout to fill holes, voids or clearances in faucets or water intake piping	70	0,11	1,0%	5,58 \$	390,85	0,63	0,2%
	i	[22] Un. Replacement ... eccentric lighting fixture	43	0,07	0,6%	22,49 \$	967,13	1,55	0,4%
	j	[23] Un. Replacement ... misalign interior partitions	22	0,04	0,3%	129,70 \$	2.853,45	4,56	1,3%
iii: Unpredictable errors	k	[24] Un. Placement where not placed... behind doors	17	0,03	0,2%	45,99 \$	781,90	1,25	0,4%
	l	[25] Un. Replacement broken/punched/hit... pieces	691	1,11	9,9%	22,49 \$	15.541,61	24,86	7,2%
Total		6.963	11,14			215.274,94	344,44		